

Zunami LLC

Oak lamellas and pellets

Producer of high-quality oak lamellas for flooring and fuel pellets from production rejects focusing on efficiency increase and waste management

Highlights of innovative features

- Large investments in high tech planning, slicing equipment and patented drying systems connecting the production processes allowed to increase the material yield of oak lamellas by 20%.
- Complete utilization of wood processing waste, including bark and sawdust, the Ukrainian company meets production standards of the leading of European woodworking enterprises
- The investments into higher process efficiency and optimized pellet production allowed for reducing production waste by 35% corresponding to the volume of 6.000 trees per year.

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (ERBD) supported Zunami in their efforts for more efficient and energy saving production processes through the FINTECC (Finance and Technology Transfer Centre for Climate Change) that is part of the EBRD's contribution towards climate technology transfer to countries in transition

Company | Ownership of innovation

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